

INVESTIGATION OF PAPER AND PULP INDUSTRY EFFLUENT INTERACTION WITH TROPICAL SOILS THROUGH RESPONSE SURFACE ANALYSIS

JAYATHEERTHA H S*

Research Scholar, Department of Civil Engineering, GITAM School of Technology, GITAM University, Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, India.
Assistant Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, Dayananda Sagar Academy of Technology and Management, Bengaluru, Karnataka, India. *Corresponding Author Email: hjayathe@gitam.in

T SRINIVAS

Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, GITAM School of Technology, GITAM University, Visakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, India.

Abstract

The effluents released by the paper and pulp industry have a harmful impact on both soil and aquatic environments. These discharges occur at regular intervals, containing varying chemical compositions, including sulphate, phosphates, cadmium, zinc, and other pollutants. Therefore, the variation in effluents collected at regular intervals also influences the geotechnical properties of soils, necessitating a thorough investigation. This paper aims at multi-objective optimization of geotechnical properties of red soil (RS) and black cotton soil (BCS) mixed with paper and pulp industry effluents (10%, 20%, and 40%) collected during the first three weeks of a month and cured for specific durations (0, 14, and 28 days). Advanced analyses including Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Energy Dispersive X-ray Analysis (EDAX), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), and X-ray Diffraction (XRD) were conducted to assess the microstructural and chemical changes in the soils. These tests confirmed significant deterioration in the properties of both RS and BCS upon addition of paper industry effluents. Response surface methodology indicated a higher desirability value of 0.8119 for BCS compared to 0.6935 for RS, demonstrating that the effluent parameters have a more pronounced effect on BCS.

Keywords: Red Soil, Geotechnical Properties, Black Cotton Soil, Response Surface Methodology.

1. INTRODUCTION

As the basis for infrastructure, agriculture, and natural ecosystems, soils are an essential part of the environment [1]. Due to substantial agricultural value and economic significance, red soil (RS) and black cotton soils (BCS) are the common types of soil available in many parts of India [2]. RS is usually found in hilly and forested regions and has crimson color due to the presence of iron oxides. RS is ideally suited for a variety of crops due to its well-drained qualities and mild fertility. BCS or Regur soil is rich in organic matter and clay, which helps to retain moisture well [3] and is important for growing cotton and other agricultural crops. Over recent decades, rapid industrialization and urbanization have resulted in the release of various effluents into the environment [4] leading to deterioration of soil health and consequently, a decline in agricultural production. In particular, the harmful effluents from paper and pulp industry possess the complex mixture of lignin, cellulose, dyes, and chemical additives which can drastically affect the geotechnical characteristics of soils [5]. For instance, increased organic content can

increase plasticity index of clayey soil, which can further impact stability and load-bearing capabilities. Hence, there is a strong rising concern for the sustainability of the environment and agricultural production over the effects of such effluents on soil permeability, compaction, structure, and overall fertility.

Few authors have reported the effect of effluents on geotechnical properties of soil. Pooja Sharma et al (2021) [9] reported that paper industry effluents contained high pollution parameters which were above the permissible limits along with the existence of heavy metals and hence suggested for a tertiary treatment before the discharge. S Vinoth et al (2021) [4] compared the properties of non-polluted and polluted medium coarse-grained soil from the effluents of dyeing industry. The authors noticed the negative impact on polluted soil parameters such as increase in heavy metallic content like Manganese (0.32%), Copper (1.04%), Lead (0.14%), Iron (5.46%) and decrease in permeability by 76.1% and specific gravity by 0.7%. Muhammad Imran Khan et al 2016 [6] blended soil with paper and textile industry effluents and compared the properties of contaminated and non-contaminated soil and concluded that contaminated soil exhibited higher OMC by 10% than non-contaminated soil, higher liquid limit by 13.5% than non-contaminated soil, higher plasticity index by 37.5% than non-contaminated soil and lower compressive strength by 5% than non-contaminated soil. Mustafa Momeni et al (2020) [11] determined the geotechnical properties of soil mixed with pH water (acidic and basic) and noticed that increase in acidity caused an increase in Atterberg limits (Liquid Limit by 11% and Plasticity Index by 6%) and decrease in California Bearing Ratio by 6% and Unconfined Compressive Strength by 4%

T Karthika et al. (2022) [12] investigated the geo-technical properties of soil contaminated by leachate and Contaminated Soil stabilized using Construction & Demolition waste. Due to the adsorption of effluents, contaminated soil properties deteriorated and once after stabilization, the properties like MDD increased from 1.9 g/cm³ to 2.2 g/cm³, OMC decreased in the range of 10 to 12%, the shear strength of the stabilized soil increased by 25%. Also, the same authors [14] studied the properties of the soil deteriorated from effluents of dyeing industry & observed increase in liquid limit by 12.4%, 40% of the soil showed increase in OMC with decrease in MDD, 30% of soil showed decrease in UCC upon mixing of effluents.

Muhammad Irfan et al. (2018) [13] blended the natural cohesive soil with effluents of dyeing & tannery industry. It was observed that Liquid Limit of the soil increased from 44.58% to 52.77%, plasticity index increased from 17.97% to 27.03%, optimum moisture content was observed to increase by around 21.9%. Vinod Kumar et al (2015) [15] reported the effect of effluent samples collected from pulp and paper mill (Uttaranchal state) on chemical properties of soil. The effluent parameters were found to exceed permissible limits and indicated the presence of heavy metals. M V Velraj et al. (2019) [16] compared the properties of clayey soil blended with effluents of dyeing industry and those with virgin soil. Polluted soil exhibited higher Atterberg Limits, swelling and shrinkage leading to shear failure of soil.

From the review of literature [1-16], it was found that some of the researchers have focused on analyzing the geotechnical performance of soils treated with effluents from various industries. Also, the effect of stabilizers such as marble dust, ground granulated blast-furnace slag (GGBS), etc. on geotechnical properties of soils has been reported. The effluents discharged from paper and pulp industry causes hazardous effect on the soil as well as aquatic environment. These effluents from the industry gets discharged in regular intervals with varying chemical composition of sulphates, phosphates, cadmium, zinc and so on. Thus, the variants of effluents collected during regular intervals also affect the geotechnical characteristics of soils which demand a comprehensive analysis characterization. The objective of the present study was to investigate the effect of effluents collected from paper and pulp industry on the geotechnical properties of red and BCS and the microstructure. The soil properties such as liquid limit, plastic limit, shrinkage limit, compressive strength (UCS) and compaction characteristics were investigated to ascertain the effect of effluents. The microstructure and chemical composition was ascertained using scanning electron microscope and energy dispersive spectrometer.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Selection of soils

BCS or Regur soil is mostly found only in few parts of Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Gujarat and Maharashtra [3]. Its high clay content gives it a unique dark color, and it has a great ability to hold onto moisture. For the present research, 20 kg of BCS was procured from Raichur District of Karnataka State and the following properties were noted as indicated in Table1. RS is commonly available soil in places like Bengaluru, and usually has a reddish color and a granular texture due to the high iron oxide content [19]. For the present research, RS was procured from Bengaluru District of Karnataka State and the following properties were noted as indicated in Table 1.

Table 1: Geotechnical Properties of BCS and RS

Properties	BCS	RS
Specific gravity	2.5	2.65
Uniformity co-efficient	2	3
Co-efficient of curvature	0.8	1
Liquid limit (%)	62	35.9
Plastic limit (%)	26.72	22.32
Shrinkage limit (%)	22.34	19.32
Max. dry density (g/cc)	1.4	1.9
Optimum moisture content (%)	19.23	14.56
Un-Confined compressive strength (kg/cm ²)	1.2	2.2
Cohesion ((kg/cm ²)	0.102	0.156
Angle of internal friction (degrees)	20	30

2.2 Selection of Effluents

The effluents of pulp and paper industry are discharged through pulping, bleaching, and finishing processes. These contain higher amounts of sulphur compounds, lignin, and

chlorinated chemicals which are detrimental to aquatic habitats [21]. The addition of these compounds to aquatic life leads to oxygen depletion which is measured in terms of high biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) [22]. The geotechnical properties of soils also get deteriorated can be considerably changed by the wastewaters produced by the paper and pulp industries [9]. Additionally, higher moisture retention might result in reduced soil structure, encouraging erosion and instability. These alterations have the potential to weaken the surrounding infrastructure and foundations over time. In the present study, paper and pulp industry effluent was adopted and its characteristics were noted as indicated in Table 2.

Table 2: Characteristics of Paper and Pulp Industry Effluents collected week wise

Parameters	Week 1 Effluent	Week 2 Effluent	Week 3 Effluent	CPCB Norms
pH	8.8	8.6	9.2	5.5-9.0
Color	956	978	986	To get diminished
BOD (mg/l)	644	684	756	30
COD (mg/l)	1624	1542	1664	250
Turbidity (NTU)	247	268	293	-
Sulphate (mg/l)	856	877	910	-
Phosphate (mg/l)	58	62	75	5
TS (mg/l)	897	886	920	-
Zinc (mg/l)	4.8	4.9	5.6	5.0
Cadmium (mg/l)	1.9	1.9	2.3	2.0

2.3 Design of Experiments

Significant parameters affecting the geotechnical properties of effluent-treated soil were identified, namely curing time (0, 14, 18 days), effluent quantity (10%, 20%, 40%), and frequency of effluent collection (week 1, week 2, week 3).

These parameters were organized into an experimental layout using Taguchi's L9 Orthogonal Array as shown in Table 3. The effluent blended soil samples were tested to measure their geotechnical properties.

Data from these tests were analyzed using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) using Minitab software. Finally, Response Surface Methodology (RSM) was adopted to optimize the geotechnical properties of the effluent-treated soil.

Table 3: Design of experiments based on Taguchi's L9 Orthogonal Array

SI No.	Curing days	Effluent quantity (%)	Frequency of Collection (Week)
1	0	10	W1
2	0	20	W2
3	0	40	W3
4	14	10	W2
5	14	20	W3
6	14	40	W1
7	28	10	W3
8	28	20	W1
9	28	40	W2

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Geotechnical properties of RS

Treatment of RS with paper and pulp industry effluent significantly altered its geotechnical properties. The liquid limit (conducted as per IS 2720 Part 5 – casagrande method) increased from 35.9% to 44% after 28 days of curing with 40% effluent, primarily influenced by the frequency of effluent collection, which accounted for 39.22% of the variation. Similarly, the plastic limit (conducted as per IS 2720 Part 4 – 3mm thread method) rose from 22.32% to 33.07% after 28 days with 10% effluent, with frequency of collection contributing 58.79% to its change. The shrinkage limit (conducted as per IS 2720 Part 6 – mercury method) increased from 19.32% to 25.3% after 14 days of curing with 20% effluent, mainly affected by effluent quantity (42.55%). Optimum moisture content (OMC) (conducted as per IS 2720 Part 7 – Standard Proctor method) also rose from 14.56% to 21.7% after 28 days with 20% effluent, with effluent quantity again playing the largest role (42.55%). Conversely, the maximum dry density (MDD) (conducted as per IS 2720 Part 7 – Standard Proctor method) dropped from 1.9 g/cc to 0.9 g/cc after 14 days with 20% effluent and was most influenced by curing days (60.90%). Unconfined compressive strength (UCS) (conducted as per IS 2720 Part 10) decreased from 2.2 to 0.6 kg/cm² after 14 days curing with 20% effluent, with curing days contributing 60.76% to this deterioration. Overall, effluent treatment deteriorated soil strength and altered its moisture-related limits, with frequency of collection, effluent quantity, and curing duration being key factors in these changes. Fig 1 depicts the responses of RS, such as liquid limit, plastic limit, and UCS, change with different treatments using paper and pulp industry effluent. Table 4 represents the various geotechnical properties of RS after treating it with effluents (tabulation as per Taguchi's L9 orthogonal array). Table 5 represents the analysis of variance (ANOVA) results which are determined using Minitab software, highlighting the significant contribution of factors such as frequency of collection, effluent quantity, and curing days to the deterioration of the soil's geotechnical properties. It can be ascertained that liquid limit and plastic limit was significantly influenced by frequency of collection. While shrinkage limit and OMC were influenced by effluent quantity, curing days influenced MDD and UCS effectively.

Table 4: Geotechnical properties of RS (as per Taguchi's L9 orthogonal array)

Experiment	Liquid Limit (%)	Plastic Limit (%)	Shrinkage Limit (%)	OMC (%)	MDD (g/cc)	UCC (kg/cm ²)
1 (0, 10%, W1)	36.9	26.3	22.6	15.72	1.74	1.4
2 (0,20%, W2)	38.4	28.5	24.3	19.5	1.7	1.6
3 (0,40%, W3)	41.4	30.68	21.8	17.8	1.2	0.8
4(14,10%, W2)	37.3	30.87	22.3	16.9	1	1
5(14,20%, W3)	50	28.4	25.3	17.35	0.9	0.6
6(14,40%, W1)	38.6	27.2	20.9	19.32	1.2	0.8
7(28,10%, W3)	42	33.07	21.4	18.3	1.4	1.4
8(28,20%, W1)	41.25	26.5	23.2	21.7	1.2	1.6
9(28,40%, W2)	44	27.5	24.7	19.3	1.2	1.4
Virgin Soil	35.9	22.32	19.32	14.56	1.9	2.2

Fig 1: variations in geotechnical properties of RS

Table 5: ANOVA of Geotechnical Properties – RS					
Property	Factors	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	Contribution (%)
Liquid Limit	Curing Days	2	21.97	10.99	16.37
	Effluent Quantity	2	30.41	15.20	22.66
	Frequency	2	52.62	26.31	39.22
	Error	2	29.16	14.58	
	Total	8	134.16		
Plastic Limit	Curing Days	2	0.4298	0.2149	1.02
	Effluent Quantity	2	8.2584	4.1292	19.62
	Frequency	2	24.7442	12.3721	58.79
	Error	2	8.6562	4.3281	
	Total	8	42.0886		
Shrinkage Limit	Curing Days	2	0.1156	0.05778	0.61
	Effluent Quantity	2	8.0689	4.03444	42.55
	Frequency	2	3.5822	1.79111	18.91
	Error	2	7.1756	3.58778	
	Total	8	18.9422		
Optimum Moisture Content (OMC)	Curing Days	2	8.064	4.0319	32.71
	Effluent Quantity	2	10.334	5.1669	41.91
	Frequency	2	1.885	0.9427	7.64
	Error	2	4.369	2.1845	
	Total	8	24.652		

Maximum Dry Density (MDD)	Curing Days	2	0.39636	0.19818	60.90
	Effluent Quantity	2	0.04969	0.02484	7.63
	Frequency	2	0.06969	0.03484	10.70
	Error	2	0.13502	0.06751	
	Total	8	0.65076		
Unconfined Compressive Strength	Curing Days	2	0.70222	0.35111	60.76
	Effluent Quantity	2	0.14222	0.07111	12.30
	Frequency	2	0.27556	0.13778	23.84
	Error	2	0.03556	0.01778	
	Total	8	1.15556		
Df – Degrees of freedom, Adj SS – adjusted sum of squares, Adj MS – adjusted mean squares.					

Fig 1: Variations in geotechnical properties of RS according L9 Orthogonal array approach

3.2 Geotechnical properties of BCS

Treatment of BCS (BCS) with paper and pulp industry effluent led to noticeable changes in its geotechnical properties.

The liquid limit increased from 62% to 69.2% (0 days curing, 40% effluent), and the plastic limit rose from 26.72% to 36.4% (14 days curing, 10% effluent), with frequency of effluent collection being the most influential factor—contributing 70.09% and 47.73% respectively according to ANOVA in Table 5.

The shrinkage limit also increased from 22.34% to 28.3% (14 days, 20% effluent), again primarily influenced by frequency of collection (46%).

Similarly, the optimum moisture content (OMC) rose from 19.23% to 23.5% (28 days, 10% effluent), with frequency of collection contributing 50.93%.

In contrast, unconfined compressive strength (UCS) dropped from 1.2 kg/cm² to 0.4 kg/cm² (0 days curing, 40% effluent), where curing days had the most impact (52.12%).

Fig 2 illustrates the variations, how each geotechnical parameter of BCS responds to varying effluent treatments.

Table 6 represents the various geotechnical properties of BCS after treating it with effluents.

Table 7 represents ANOVA results confirming the dominant influence of collection frequency and curing duration on soil properties.

Fig 2: Variations in geotechnical properties of BCS according L9 Orthogonal array approach.

Table 6: Geotechnical properties of BCS (tabulation as per Taguchi's L9 orthogonal array)

Experiment	Liquid Limit (%)	Plastic Limit (%)	Shrinkage Limit (%)	OMC (%)	MDD (g/cc)	UCC (kg/cm²)
1 (0, 10%, W1)	65	28.3	23.6	20.72	1.2	0.7
2 (0,20%, W2)	63.2	29.3	26.5	21.5	0.9	0.6
3 (0,40%, W3)	69.2	33.2	27.3	22.3	0.8	0.4
4(14,10%, W2)	63.2	36.4	25.2	21.4	1.3	0.4
5(14,20%, W3)	67.4	33.2	28.3	22.6	0.7	0.4
6(14,40%, W1)	66.4	29.8	24.8	21.8	0.9	0.6
7(28,10%, W3)	66.3	34.5	25.9	23.5	0.7	0.6
8(28,20%, W1)	68.2	29.3	26.2	22.7	0.7	0.8
9(28,40%, W2)	64.6	29.8	27.9	21.6	0.8	0.8
Virgin Soil	62	26.72	22.34	19.23	1.4	1.2

Property	Factors	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	Contribution (%)
Liquid Limit	Curing Days	2	0.8289	0.4144	2.30
	Effluent Quantity	2	5.8822	2.9411	16.38
	Frequency	2	25.1622	12.5811	70.08
	Error	2	4.0289	2.0144	
	Total	8	35.9022		
Plastic Limit	Curing Days	2	12.83	6.413	19.89
	Effluent Quantity	2	10.75	5.373	16.67
	Frequency	2	30.78	15.390	47.73
	Error	2	10.13	5.063	
	Total	8	64.48		

Shrinkage Limit	Curing Days	2	1.162	0.5811	6.31
	Effluent Quantity	2	7.642	3.8211	41.51
	Frequency	2	8.469	4.2344	46.00
	Error	2	1.136	0.5678	
	Total	8	18.409		
Optimum Moisture Content	Curing Days	2	1.8219	0.9109	32.32
	Effluent Quantity	2	0.2899	0.1449	05.14
	Frequency	2	2.8712	1.4356	50.93
	Error	2	0.6539	0.3269	
	Total	8	5.6368		
Maximum Dry Density (MDD)	Curing Days	2	0.10889	0.054444	27.97
	Effluent Quantity	2	0.14889	0.074444	38.28
	Frequency	2	0.11556	0.057778	29.71
	Error	2	0.01556	0.007778	
	Total	8	0.38889		
Unconfined Compressive Strength (UCS)	Curing Days	2	0.108889	0.054444	52.12
	Effluent Quantity	2	0.002222	0.001111	1.063
	Frequency	2	0.082222	0.041111	39.36
	Error	2	0.015556	0.007778	
	Total	8	0.208889		

Df – Degrees of freedom, Adj SS – adjusted sum of squares, Adj MS – adjusted mean squares.

3.3 Simultaneous Optimization of Responses

Multi objective optimization of geotechnical responses of RS and BCS was performed using response surface methodology (RSM). RSM is a collection of mathematical and statistical methods and adopts design of experiments for developing, enhancing and optimizing processes in engineering, chemistry, and other applied sciences.

A desirability function approach in RSM is used to simultaneously optimize the responses $y_1, y_2, y_3, \dots, y_n$. These responses are transformed into comparable values in the range $0 < d < 1$. The response having d value closer to unity is considered to be acceptable and that closer to zero is kept outside the acceptable region.

Then the aim is to maximize the geometric mean of individual composite desirability values of responses i.e. $\text{maximise } (d) = \sqrt{d_1 \times d_2 \times \dots \times d_n}$.

Multi objective optimization plot of the responses of RS and BCS is as shown in Fig 3 and Fig 4 respectively. It was found that the properties of RS got more deteriorated at 16 days of curing with 27% effluent quantity and week 3 effluent.

Similarly, the properties of BCS got deteriorated at 14 days of curing with 20% effluent quantity and week 3 effluent. As shown in the optimization curve, RS had desirability value of 0.6935 nearing to 1 (one) which indicates that the responses are acceptable. Fig 4 shows the optimization curve for BCS having optimal value of 0.8119 which is also nearing to one and the responses are acceptable.

Fig 3: Multi objective Optimization of RS Properties

Fig 4: Multi objective Optimization of BCS Properties

3.4 Characterization of Soil Samples

The microstructure of virgin BCS is as shown in Fig 5(a)-(b) at different magnifications. The plate-shaped and flake-like microstructure was observed in clay minerals. Moderate porosity was indicated by the soil's uneven, loosely packed structure and inter-particle gaps. The existence of fine-grained, highly flexible clay is suggested by the thin, overlapping sheets and unevenly edged platelets. In several areas, the particles exhibit a discernible alignment, suggesting compaction and natural deposition. Thus, the virgin BCS exhibits a cohesive structure with a reasonably large surface area and the capacity to hold moisture, which is consistent with its well-known geotechnical characteristics of high plasticity and low permeability.

Fig 5: Microstructure of Virgin BCS at magnification of a) 500 x b) 1000 x

The microstructure of BCS treated with paper mill effluent exhibits deterioration when compared to its virgin form which is as shown in micrographs at different magnifications in Fig 6 (a) – (b). More irregular, fragmented particles were observed in the treated soil, replacing the formerly distinct flaky and plate-like pattern characteristics of clay rich in montmorillonite. Increased grain spacing and the absence of cemented or aggregated clusters, which were present in the undisturbed soil, indicate a noticeable weakening of inter-particle connection. Larger voids and irregular pore structures indicate a disrupted and loosened matrix and there is a noticeable increase in porosity. Particle surfaces in some areas seem smoother or coated may be as a result of organic fibers or chemical residues from the effluent which could help to lower inter-particle cohesion and friction. Thus BCS mixed with paper effluent is supported by the reduction in bonding strength as shown in Fig 6c and the increase in internal voids. The disturbance of the compact particle structure also probably contributes to the soil's expanded behavior, making it a more unstable and moisture-sensitive substance.

Fig 6: Microstructure of Effluent blended BCS at magnification of a) 1000 x b) 2000 x c) 3500 x

The microstructure of virgin RS as shown Fig 7 (a) – (b) reveals a heterogeneous surface morphology characterized by irregularly shaped particles. The soil particles appear smooth and are loosely packed with noticeable voids and uneven surfaces, dense grains indicating a naturally porous structure.

These pores contribute significantly to the soil's permeability and water retention capacity.

The particles display a range of sizes, suggesting the presence of both clay and silt fractions. The overall texture appears rough, with several particles showing flaky or platy structures. This is typical of kaolinite-rich soils, which are often dominant in RSs.

The lack of any distinct layering or alignment suggests minimal compaction or anthropogenic alteration. Moreover, the absence of surface coatings indicates the virgin nature of the sample.

No fibrous or granular industrial residues are evident. The soil shows characteristics consistent with natural weathering and mineral disintegration.

The particle edges become more defined, revealing jagged and angular contours, which indicate limited mechanical weathering. Small pores and interstitial spaces can be seen more prominently, confirming the soil's potential for moisture absorption.

Some fine particulates are loosely attached to the surfaces of larger aggregates, possibly due to electrostatic forces or natural adhesion. There is no evidence of sintering or fusing among particles, which further supports the untouched condition of the soil.

Textural differences among the particles suggest a mineralogical diversity, likely including oxides of iron and aluminum common in RSs.

The high-resolution view does not show any crystalline or amorphous overlays that would indicate contamination. These microstructural traits point toward a natural genesis and stability in the soil's physicochemical makeup.

The variation in particle morphology is consistent with a non-industrial environment.

Fig 7: Microstructure of Effluent virgin RS at magnification of a) 500 x b)5000 x

The microstructures of the effluent-treated RS are as shown in Fig 8 (a) – (b) at different magnifications. The particles show signs of clumping and fusion, likely due to deposition of dissolved solids from the effluent.

A notable observation is the masking of fine pore spaces and the smoothing of micro-surfaces, which would typically host microbial activity or water retention features. In the fig 8c, degradation is most apparent.

In contrast to the virgin soil's open and textured structure, this treated sample shows advanced signs of fragmentation and surface erosion.

These morphological degradations highlight the urgent need for remediation strategies when such effluent is released into agricultural zones.

Fig 8: Microstructure of Effluent blended RS at magnification of a) 500 x b) 5000 x c) 10000 x

3.4.5 Analysis of Chemical Composition

Fig 9 represents EDAX analysis of virgin BCS (BCS) which reveals a mineralogically rich and chemically stable composition, dominated by silica-based and alumino-silicate compounds. The major oxide present is Silicon Dioxide (75.38%), indicating a silicate-dominant framework that contributes to particle rigidity and internal friction. Aluminum Oxide (Al_2O_3) at 11.93 % further supports the presence of clay minerals such as montmorillonite, which are known for their plasticity and moisture retention. The presence of Iron Oxide (Fe_2O_3) at 5.29 % suggests moderate natural cementation and contributes to inter-particle bonding and overall soil cohesion. Minor oxides like Magnesium Oxide (MgO) and Potassium Oxide (K_2O) help maintain ionic stability, while the low sulfur content (SO_3 at 0.96%) confirms minimal contamination from salts or industrial byproducts. This composition reflects a balanced, naturally bonded clay system, capable of sustaining structural strength under geotechnical applications. Mineralogical Implications from XRD Pattern as shown in fig 10 shows dominance of quartz and albite in the XRD pattern of virgin BCS and suggests a mineral assemblage with strong internal bonding and a resistance to structural breakdown.

Fig 9: EDAX data of virgin BCS

Fig 10: XRD Pattern of Virgin BCS

The EDAX spectrum of BCS treated with paper industry effluent as shown in fig 11 reveals substantial alterations in chemical composition that indicate degradation.

The most critical observation is the decrease in Silicon Dioxide (SiO_2) from 75.38% to 62.05%, reflecting a disruption in the silicate-based mineral framework that forms the structural backbone of the soil.

While Aluminum Oxide (Al_2O_3) increases from 11.93% to 15.26%, the drop in SiO_2 signals potential disintegration of aluminosilicate bonds, which play a vital role in clay strength and plasticity. Iron Oxide (Fe_2O_3) levels nearly double, suggesting oxidative changes that may contribute to weaker, flaky mineral phases.

Additionally, the elevated presence of Sodium (Na_2O), Potassium (K_2O), and Calcium Oxide (CaO) points to chemical intrusion from the effluent, introducing soluble salts that can affect interparticle bonding.

Mineralogical Evidence of Degradation from XRD Patterns as shown in fig 12 reveals the reference pattern list which highlights Quartz, Albite, and notably, Dolomite in the treated sample — a new phase absent in the virgin BCS.

The emergence of dolomite implies chemical contamination or precipitation of salts, likely introduced through effluent interaction. Dolomite's presence can disrupt the clay mineral network and create zones of non-cohesive or brittle behavior.

The FTIR spectrum as shown in Fig 13 reveals noticeable reduction in the broad O–H stretching peak around 3400 cm^{-1} suggests loss or weakening of hydroxyl groups, which are essential for maintaining interlayer bonding and moisture retention in clay minerals.

The H–O–H bending peak near 1650 cm^{-1} , indicative of bound water, appears suppressed or shifted, implying dehydration or disruption of the hydrated clay lattice.

Fig 11: EDAX data of effluent treated BCS

Fig 12: XRD pattern of effluent treated BCS

Fig 13: FTIR spectrum of effluent treated BCS

EDAX analysis of Virgin RS as shown in fig 14 reveals a composition dominated by silicate and iron oxide minerals. The most abundant compound detected is SiO₂ (Silicon Dioxide), comprising 36.58% by weight and 53.37% by atomic percentage, indicating a quartz-rich or silicate-heavy matrix, typical of well-weathered RSs. This high silica content contributes to the soil's granular texture and low plasticity. Fe₂O₃ (Ferric Oxide) is the second most prominent compound, constituting 36.26% by weight, reflecting the presence of iron-rich minerals like hematite or goethite, which are responsible for the red coloration. Together, these oxides suggest a mineralogically mature soil that has

undergone significant weathering and oxidation. The X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis of the Virgin RS as shown in fig 15 reveals a mineralogical composition dominated by quartz (SiO_2), as indicated by the strong peak at $28.03^\circ 2\theta$ with 100% relative intensity and a d-spacing of 3.17996 \AA .

Fig 14: EDAX data of virgin RS

Fig 15: XRD Mineralogical composition in virgin RS

EDAX results for the Effluent-Treated RS as shown in fig 16 shows a major shift in chemical composition compared to the virgin sample. SiO_2 (Silicon Dioxide) remains dominant at 54.18% by weight and 65.15% by atomic percent, which is significantly higher than in the virgin sample.

This could be attributed to effluent-induced leaching or precipitation of silica-based compounds. A marked increase is also seen in Al_2O_3 (33.05%), suggesting enrichment in alumino-silicate content, potentially from chemical reactions between the soil and effluent constituents.

Conversely, Fe_2O_3 levels dropped sharply to 5.25%, indicating substantial depletion of iron oxides, possibly due to solubilization or redox reactions triggered by the effluent. The X-ray diffraction (XRD) results of the Effluent-Treated RS as shown in fig 17 reveals notable shifts in mineralogical composition when compared to the Virgin RS.

The emergence of oligoclase and the altered peak profiles in the Effluent-Treated RS sample indicate significant changes in the mineral structure due to prolonged exposure to industrial effluent.

These changes could be the result of ion exchange reactions, pH shifts, and the deposition of effluent-derived solutes such as sodium, calcium, and silicates. Fig 18 represents TIR spectrum of Effluent-Treated RS.

The broad O–H stretching band ($3600\text{--}3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$), typically strong in untreated soils due to hydroxyl groups in clay minerals, appears slightly diminished or broadened, suggesting either structural disruption of clay minerals or replacement of surface-bound water.

Peaks in the 2920 cm^{-1} region, attributed to aliphatic C–H stretching, are more pronounced, possibly due to the adsorption of organic compounds from the effluent.

Fig 16: EDAX data of effluent treated RS

Fig 17: XRD Pattern of effluent treated RS

Fig 18: FTIR spectrum of effluent treated RS

CONCLUSIONS

The investigation of effect of effluent parameters on geotechnical properties of RS and BCS lead to the following conclusions:

1. As indicated by ANOVA, the liquid limit of RS got increased by 16 % when treated with effluent collected in second week and cured for 28 days. Similarly, the plastic limit, shrinkage limit, optimum moisture content got enhanced by 10 %, 6 %, and 7% respectively. On the other hand, MDD and UCS got decreased by 52.6 % and 72.7 % respectively after treating with effluent of third week and 14 days of curing period.

2. The liquid limit, plastic limit, shrinkage limit and OMC of BCS increased by 7.2 %, 9.6 %, 5.96 %, 4.27 % respectively. MDD and UCS got decreased by 50 % and 66.66 % respectively as indicated by ANOVA.
3. The response surface methodology optimization curve for RS, with a desirability value of 0.6935 approaching 1, indicates that the responses are acceptable. Similarly, the optimization curve for BCS (BCS), with an optimal value of 0.8119, also nearing 1, confirmed the acceptability of the responses.
4. SEM Analysis of Virgin soils (RS and BCS) exhibit dense, compact microstructures, whereas effluent-treated samples show increased porosity, microcracks, and surface roughness—indicating structural degradation due to effluent exposure.
5. EDAX analysis of Effluent-treated soils reveal altered elemental composition, notably elevated levels of sodium and chlorine, suggesting ion exchange and salt accumulation from effluent infiltration, which negatively impacts soil health.
6. XRD analysis shows a noticeable reduction in peak intensities and slight shifting in treated soils which reflect partial mineralogical transformation and decreased crystallinity, especially affecting clay minerals like montmorillonite in BCS.
7. FTIR Analysis of Effluent-treated soils show diminished or shifted functional group peaks (e.g., O-H, Si-O, Al-O), confirming chemical interaction and breakdown of native clay and oxide bonds, leading to loss of natural binding properties.

References

- 1) Bullock, Peter, and Peter J. Gregory, eds. *Soils in the urban environment*. John Wiley & Sons, 1991. ISBN: 9781444310603.
- 2) Mohammed, Syed Abu Sayeed, P. F. Sanaula, and Arif Ali Baig Moghal. "Sustainable use of locally available red earth and BCSs in retaining Cd 2+ and Ni 2+ from aqueous solutions." *International Journal of Civil Engineering* 14 (2016): 491-505.
- 3) Bharani, S., G. Ramesh Kumar, J. Ranjithkumar, G. Boopathi, and G. Singaravelu. "Experimental study of regur soil stabilization by using Non-metallic waste bottles." *Materials Today: Proceedings* 52 (2022): 1598-1602.
- 4) Vinoth, S., V. Rajeshkumar, T. Sivabalan, M. Surya, M. Thamilkumaran, and S. Saiprakash. "Impact of industrial effluents on geotechnical properties of soil." *Materials Today: Proceedings* 37 (2021): 2636-2643.
- 5) Singh, Ajay Kumar, Adarsh Kumar, and Ram Chandra. "Environmental pollutants of paper industry wastewater and their toxic effects on human health and ecosystem." *Bioresource Technology Reports* 20 (2022): 101250.
- 6) Khan, Muhammad Imran, Muhammad Irfan, Mubashir Aziz, and Ammad Hassan Khan. "Geotechnical characteristics of effluent contaminated cohesive soils." *Journal of Environmental Engineering and Landscape Management* 25, no. 1 (2017): 75-82.
- 7) Ibrahim, Omar Adnan, Ali Firat Çabalar, and Muhamd Dafer Abdulnafaa. "Improving some geotechnical properties of an organic soil using crushed waste concrete." *The International Journal of Energy & Engineering Sciences* 3, no. 3 (2018): 100-112.

- 8) Ansari, Farid. "Risk probability of soil and groundwater pollution due to leaching effect of distillery effluent used for agricultural purpose." *Int. J. Scientific Res. Env. Sci* 2, no. 2 (2014): 63-73.
- 9) Sharma, Pooja, Hafiz MN Iqbal, and Ram Chandra. "Evaluation of pollution parameters and toxic elements in wastewater of pulp and paper industries in India: A case study." *Case Studies in Chemical and Environmental Engineering* 5 (2022): 100163.
- 10) Jia, Y. G., Q. Wu, H. Shang, Zh N. Yang, and H. X. Shan. "The influence of oil contamination on the geotechnical properties of coastal sediments in the Yellow River Delta, China." *Bulletin of Engineering Geology and the Environment* 70 (2011): 517-525.
- 11) Momeni, Mustafa, Meysam Bayat, and Rassoul Ajalloeian. "Laboratory investigation on the effects of pH-induced changes on geotechnical characteristics of clay soil." *Geomechanics and Geoengineering* 17, no. 1 (2022): 188-196.
- 12) Karthika, T., K. Arumugam, R. K. Sangeetha, and A. Rajesh Kumar. "Effects on geotechnical properties of soil by leachate in landfill vicinity: Cauvery River, Pallipalayam, India." *Materials Today: Proceedings* 59 (2022): 764-768.
- 13) Irfan, Muhammad, Yulong Chen, Muhammad Ali, Muhammad Abrar, Ahmed Qadri, and Osama Bhutta. "Geotechnical properties of effluent-contaminated cohesive soils and their stabilization using industrial by-products." *Processes* 6, no. 10 (2018): 203.
- 14) Karthika, T., S. Shalini, P. S. Kothai, and K. Arumugam. "Impact of dyeing industry effluents on geotechnical properties of soil." In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 2070, no. 1, p. 012233. IOP Publishing, 2021.
- 15) Kumar, Vinod, A. K. Chopra, Sandeep Kumar, Jogendra Singh, and Roushan K. Thakur. "Effects of pulp and paper mill effluent disposal on soil characteristics in the vicinity of Uttaranchal Pulp and Paper Mill, Haridwar (Uttarakhand), India." *International Journal of Agricultural Science Research* 4, no. 6 (2015): 117-125.
- 16) Velraj, M. V., R. Narmadha, and T. Pratheep. "A comparative study of the effect of industrial waste on geotechnical properties of soil." *Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems* Vol. 12. Sp- 2 / 2019.
- 17) Gidigasu, S. S. R., and S. K. Gawu. "The mode of formation, nature and geotechnical characteristics of BCSS-a review." *Sci Res Essays* 1 (2013): 377-90.
- 18) Oza, J. B., and P. J. Gundaliya. "Study of BCS characteristics with cement waste dust and lime." *Procedia Engineering* 51 (2013): 110-118.
- 19) Prasetyo, B. H., and R. J. Gilkes. "Properties of iron-oxides from RSs derived from volcanic tuff in West Java." *Soil Research* 32, no. 4 (1994): 781-794.
- 20) Amiri, Mohammad, Mahmood Sanjari, and Fatemeh Porhonor. "Microstructural evaluation of the cement stabilization of hematite-rich RS." *Case Studies in Construction Materials* 16 (2022): e00935.
- 21) Giri, Jitendra, Anjana Srivastava, S. P. Pachauri, and P. C. Srivastava. "Effluents from paper and pulp industries and their impact on soil properties and chemical composition of plants in Uttarakhand, India." *J Environ Waste Manag* 1, no. 1 (2014): 26-30.
- 22) Tripathi, Pooja, Virendra Kumar, Gyanesh Joshi, Sat Pal Singh, Suresh Panwar, Sanjay Naithani, and Raman Nautiyal. "A comparative study on physico-chemical properties of pulp and paper mill effluent." *International Journal of Engineering Research and Applications* 3, no. 6 (2013): 811-818.